

PRACTICAL TEACHING AND ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATIVE ABILITY OF STUDENTS IN SELECTED COLLEGES IN HUNAN PROVINCE

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Practical Teaching and Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability of Students in Selected Colleges in Hunan Province

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Abstract

Aiming at the current demand of college students' entrepreneurial innovative ability cultivation, this study explores the relationship between practical teaching quality and students' entrepreneurial innovative ability in three universities in Hunan Province, China. In order to meet the challenges of improving the success rate of entrepreneurship, promoting employment and easing the employment pressure of graduates, this study adopted a descriptive-comparative-correlational research design, and evaluated the teaching quality from three aspects of practice input, process and effect through a questionnaire survey, and evaluated the performance of students from three aspects of innovation ability, entrepreneurial thinking and practical ability. According to SPSS Statistics 26 calculation, there is a strong correlation between entrepreneurial innovation ability and practical teaching quality (0.69). The results show that improving the quality of practical teaching can significantly enhance students' entrepreneurial innovative ability. Based on this, the paper puts forward a development program to improve practical teaching in order to promote the development of innovation and entrepreneurship education in colleges and universities.

Keywords: *practical teaching, entrepreneurial innovative ability, development program*

Introduction

In recent years, research on innovation and entrepreneurship has shifted focus from entrepreneurs to college students, particularly in China. In 2010, the Ministry of Education emphasized innovation and entrepreneurship education for all college students, aiming to enhance their awareness and abilities. Subsequent policies in 2016 and 2017 further stressed cultivating independent innovation and entrepreneurial skills. Government reports in 2019 and 2021 prioritized supporting mass entrepreneurship to drive employment, highlighting the role of entrepreneurial innovation in improving success rates and alleviating job market pressures for graduates.

The focus on developing students' entrepreneurial capabilities has led to an emphasis on dual-creation courses, integration of professional knowledge with civic education, and industry-education collaboration. The rise of the digital economy, network platforms, and social media has provided new opportunities and challenges for fostering innovation, guided by the characteristics of big data. Current educational approaches stress the importance of creating a comprehensive ecosystem involving universities, enterprises, and students, with support from social institutions and proactive engagement from university leadership.

Globally, initiatives like the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) highlight the importance of education in driving innovation, entrepreneurship, and economic growth (UNESCO, 2015). Countries are reassessing educational strategies to ensure graduates are equipped with both theoretical knowledge and practical skills to navigate complex, modern economies (Marginson, 2018; World Economic Forum, 2019). Practice teaching is seen as crucial in this regard; it provides a framework that includes objectives, curriculum, and evaluation, integrates innovation with professional practices, and fosters creative problem-solving and entrepreneurial thinking. It offers a practical path to nurturing innovation and entrepreneurship across different disciplines, enhancing students' abilities to tackle real-world challenges.

While many researchers have acknowledged the role of practice teaching, most existing studies have been theoretical, lacking quantitative exploration of the relationship between teaching quality and entrepreneurial capability. There are few studies that analyze how specific elements of practical teaching influence the development of innovative and entrepreneurial skills quantitatively. This research seeks to address these gaps by providing a comprehensive, data-driven analysis of the relationship between practical teaching quality and the cultivation of entrepreneurial innovative abilities, aiming to offer actionable insights for educational practice.

The researcher has extensive experience in academic affairs, including six years as director of the Academic Affairs Office, focusing on achieving educational goals and evaluating teaching quality. Key questions include: What is the relationship between practical teaching quality and the development of innovation and entrepreneurship? Which aspects of practical teaching are most crucial for cultivating these abilities? How can practical teaching quality be enhanced to further improve students' entrepreneurial skills? This study's quantitative approach aims to answer these questions, offering a reference for future improvements in educational strategies.

Research Questions

This research explored the relationship between the quality of practical teaching and the entrepreneurial innovative ability of students in selected colleges in Hunan province. Specifically, the following problems were answered:

1. What is the profile of the student respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex;

- 1.2. age;
- 1.3. academic year; and
- 1.4. major of study?
2. What is the level of assessment of student respondents on the quality of practical teaching in terms of:
 - 2.1. practical teaching input;
 - 2.2. practical teaching process; and
 - 2.3. practical teaching effect?
3. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the quality of practical teaching of student respondents when the profile is taken as a test factor?
4. What is the level of assessment on entrepreneurial innovative ability of student respondents in terms of:
 - 4.1. global innovative thinking;
 - 4.2. entrepreneurial literacy; and
 - 4.3. practical ability?
5. Is there significant difference in the assessment of the entrepreneurial innovative ability of the student respondents when the profile is taken as test factors?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the quality of practical teaching and entrepreneurial innovative ability on the assessment of student respondents?
7. Based on the findings, what program can be proposed to improve the quality of practical teaching?

Literature Review

Practical Teaching

Practical teaching refers to the collective term for all practical aspects of the undergraduate teaching process, such as experiments, practical training, internships, course design (Practicum), and other related elements. In recent years, the research of practical teaching quality evaluation has become the key research direction to improve the quality of practical teaching (Liu and Yang, 2023). Zhu et al. (2023) discussed the construction of the quality evaluation system of practical teaching in applied undergraduate colleges, pointed out the problems existing in the current system, and proposed the construction of a scientific and effective evaluation system to improve the quality of talent training.

Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability

Entrepreneurial innovative ability refers to the combination of innovative thinking and entrepreneurial literacy, and the ability to put innovative ideas into practice, which is a comprehensive ability composed of innovative thinking, entrepreneurial literacy, and practical ability. With the rise of the concept of "mass innovation and innovation", the cultivation of college students' innovation and entrepreneurship ability has become an important issue in Chinese higher education. Wang and Liu (2020) pointed out that the cultivation of college students' innovation ability is an inevitable requirement for the construction of an innovation-oriented country, and high innovation ability is an important condition and guarantee for the success of innovation and entrepreneurship. College students also strongly agree on the importance of innovation ability. In the era of new engineering, Fang (2024) emphasizes the necessity of building a perfect dual-creation curriculum system and actively changing the teaching mode through the case of Qilu University of Technology.

Practical Teaching Quality and Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability

The combination of innovation entrepreneurship and professional practice solves the contradiction between the development needs of the industry and the practical teaching of engineering majors. Wang (2022) focuses on the practical teaching of western economics and emphasizes that colleges and universities should strengthen the practical teaching of western economics in the context of innovation and entrepreneurship education. Wang and Du (2022) put forward the practice teaching system from the two levels of professional practice ability cultivation and innovation practice ability cultivation, discussed the reform implementation process of software engineering specialty, and then discussed the organic integration of innovation and entrepreneurship and professional practice.

Methodology

Research Design

This research employed a descriptive-comparative-correlational design to assess the levels of students' perceptions of practical teaching quality and entrepreneurial innovation ability, and to examine the relationship between these two variables across three selected colleges in Hunan. The findings aim to provide recommendations for improvement.. This approach applies to this research because descriptive research allows for a comprehensive exploration of the variables while correlational design allows for an examination of the relationship between them (Fraenkel et al., 2018).

Respondents

There are 18 public colleges in Hunan Province. In this research, three colleges were randomly selected from these colleges using a

simple random sampling method. Participants were then randomly selected from the students enrolled in these selected colleges, ensuring a representation of students from different regions of Hunan Province. Each student had an equal chance of being included in the sample, which resulted in a total sample size of 381 based on the Qualtrics Calculator, given that the total number of students in the three selected schools is 40,936.

Instrument

A researcher-made questionnaire was developed to gather data on practical teaching quality and entrepreneurial innovative ability. It consists of three parts: student profiles, assessment of practical teaching quality, and self-evaluation of entrepreneurial innovative ability. The questionnaire was designed following a comprehensive literature review and professional insights, identifying key indicators for both variables. Topics included practice teaching input, process, effect, innovative thinking, entrepreneurial literacy, and practical skills. To ensure content validity, experts reviewed the questionnaire, and pilot testing was conducted to identify issues and refine clarity. With a reliability score of 0.947 and validity score of 0.928, the questionnaire was confirmed to be valid and reliable. This process ensured that the questionnaire effectively covered essential aspects of practical teaching and entrepreneurial innovation.

Procedure

The research process involved several key steps. First, the researcher obtained permission from selected colleges by submitting a research plan and an ethical review application to their ethics committees. Following approval, formal communications were sent to the colleges, outlining the research's purpose, significance, and required collaboration, along with a consent form to ensure transparency and ethical standards. After gaining permission, respondents were randomly selected from undergraduate students, and questionnaires were distributed via WeChat, QQ, or email. Data collection took place over one week in May 2024, with students completing the questionnaires voluntarily. Subsequently, data processing and statistical analysis were conducted, leading to the interpretation of results in June-July 2024, which explored the relationship between practical teaching quality and entrepreneurial innovation.

Ethical Considerations

The ethical considerations for this research focused on several key aspects. To prevent conflicts of interest, the researcher maintained independence and impartiality. Privacy and confidentiality were ensured by protecting respondents' personal information and restricting access to data. Informed consent was obtained from all participants through detailed consent forms outlining the research's purpose, risks, and benefits. Special attention was given to vulnerable groups, such as underage students and individuals with cognitive limitations, ensuring they understood the research and obtained necessary guardian consent. Recruitment was conducted electronically with clear instructions. The study emphasized voluntary participation and confidentiality to alleviate social pressure and encourage honest responses. Risks were assessed and minimized, and the research aimed to enhance educational practices and policies while ensuring academic integrity. Overall, the research sought to positively impact educational equity, employment opportunities, and societal development through its findings.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions. To find out the differences and correlations between variables, difference analysis and correlation analysis was computed using IBM SPSS 26.0.

The profile of the student respondents

Table 1. *Profile of Respondents*

<i>Profile of the respondents</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Sex		
Male	216	56.7
Female	165	43.3
Total	381	100.0
Age		
18-20	186	48.8
Above 20	195	51.2
Total	381	100.0
Academic Year		
Freshman	101	26.5
Sophomore	124	32.5
Junior	83	21.8
Senior	73	19.2
Total	381	100.0
Major of study		
Science and engineering	206	54.1
Liberal arts	175	45.9
Total	381	100.0

Table 1 presents a comprehensive profile of the respondents, detailing their sex, age, academic year, and major of study. A total of 381 respondents participated in the study, with a male predominance of 216 respondents (56.7%) compared to 165 female respondents (43.3%).

Assessment on Quality of Practical Teaching

Table 2. Overall Level of Quality of Practical Teaching

Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description/Interpretation
Practical Teaching Input	2.52	0.46	Agree/Satisfied
Practical Teaching Process	2.63	0.50	Agree/Satisfied
Practical Teaching Effect	2.59	0.40	Agree/Satisfied
Over-All Mean	2.58	0.37	Agree/Satisfied

Legend Scale: 3.51-4.00 Strongly Agree/Strongly Satisfied; 2.51-3.50 Agree/Satisfied; 1.51-2.50 Slightly Disagree/ Slightly Dissatisfied; 1.00-1.50 Disagree/Dissatisfied.

Table 2 presents the overall level of quality of practical teaching, evaluated through three main factors: Practical Teaching Input, Practical Teaching Process, and Practical Teaching Effect. Each factor is rated based on its mean score and standard deviation, accompanied by an interpretation.

The overall mean score across all factors is 2.58, with a standard deviation of 0.37, leading to an "Agree/Satisfied" interpretation. This comprehensive evaluation indicates a general satisfaction and agreement with the quality of practical teaching among the respondents.

Yang (2022) found in his research that the overall quality of practice teaching is good, but the input and process of practice teaching are relatively weak.

Therefore, more attention should be paid to the collaborative development of production, study and research in practice teaching in the follow-up practice teaching, so as to enhance the innovation of practice results, stimulate the creativity of students, and constantly improve the quality of talent training.

In general, the data of this study show that although the overall quality of practical teaching is good, it still needs to be further improved, especially in the advanced teaching concept, the allocation of teaching teachers and the arrangement of class hours.

Differences in the Assessment of Respondents on the Quality of Practical Teaching

Table 3. Differences in the Assessment of Respondents on the Quality of Practical Teaching According to Sex

Practical Teaching	Sex	Mean	Std. Deviation	T-test value	Sig Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Practical Teaching Input	Male	2.67	0.38	8.04	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Female	2.31	0.47				
Practical Teaching Process	Male	2.72	0.47	4.17	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Female	2.51	0.51				
Practical Teaching Output	Male	2.71	0.34	6.95	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Female	2.44	0.42				
Over-All Mean	Male	2.70	0.33	7.71	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Female	2.42	0.38				

Level of Significance at 0.05.

Table 3 presents the overall mean score across all categories is 2.70 for males with a standard deviation of 0.33, and 2.42 for females with a standard deviation of 0.38. The T-test value of 7.71 and a significance value of 0.00 led to the rejection of Ho, confirming a significant difference between the assessments of male and female respondents regarding the quality of practical teaching.

Table 4. Differences in the Assessment of Respondents on the Quality of Practical Teaching According to Age

Practical Teaching	Age	Mean	Std. Deviation	T-test value	Sig Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Practical Teaching Input	18-20	2.40	0.45	-5.00	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Above 20	2.63	0.44				
Practical Teaching Process	18-20	2.55	0.51	-3.07	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Above 20	2.70	0.48				
Practical Teaching Output	18-20	2.49	0.39	-5.17	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Above 20	2.69	0.38				
Over-All Mean	18-20	2.48	0.36	-5.27	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Above 20	2.67	0.37				

Level of Significance at 0.05.

The overall mean score across all categories is 2.48 for respondents aged 18-20 with a standard deviation of 0.36, and 2.67 for those above 20 with a standard deviation of 0.37.

The T-test value of -5.27 and a significance value of 0.00 lead to the rejection of Ho, confirming a significant difference between the assessments of the two age groups regarding the quality of practical teaching.

Table 5. Differences in the Assessment of Respondents on the Quality of Practical Teaching According to Academic Year

Practical Teaching	Academic Year	Mean	Std. Deviation	F-test value	Sig Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Practical Teaching Input	Freshman	2.42	0.54	2.65	0.05	Accepted	No Significant
	Sophomore	2.51	0.40				
	Junior	2.56	0.38				
	Senior	2.61	0.47				
Practical Teaching Process	Freshman	2.60	0.55	1.18	0.32	Accepted	No Significant
	Sophomore	2.61	0.47				
	Junior	2.60	0.49				
	Senior	2.73	0.50				
Practical Teaching Output	Freshman	2.50	0.46	4.10	0.01	Rejected	Significant
	Sophomore	2.58	0.35				
	Junior	2.62	0.35				
	Senior	2.70	0.40				
Over-All Mean	Freshman	2.51	0.44	3.08	0.03	Rejected	Significant
	Sophomore	2.57	0.33				
	Junior	2.59	0.33				
	Senior	2.68	0.38				

Level of Significance at 0.05.

The overall mean score across all categories is 2.51 for freshmen with a standard deviation of 0.44, 2.57 for sophomores with a standard deviation of 0.33, 2.59 for juniors with a standard deviation of 0.33, and 2.68 for seniors with a standard deviation of 0.38. The F-test value is 3.08 with a significance value of 0.03, leading to the rejection of Ho and confirming a significant difference among the academic years regarding the overall quality of practical teaching.

Table 6. Differences in the Assessment of Respondents on the Quality of Practical Teaching According to Major of Study

Practical Teaching	Major of study	Mean	Std. Deviation	T-test value	Sig Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Practical Teaching Input	Science and Engineering	2.61	0.39	4.58	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Liberal Arts	2.40	0.50				
Practical Teaching Process	Science and Engineering	2.69	0.45	2.73	0.01	Rejected	Significant
	Liberal Arts	2.55	0.55				
Practical Teaching Output	Science and Engineering	2.73	0.31	7.53	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Liberal Arts	2.43	0.42				
Over-All Mean	Science and Engineering	2.68	0.31	5.72	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Liberal Arts	2.46	0.41				

Level of Significance at 0.05.

The overall mean score across all categories is 2.68 for Science and Engineering majors with a standard deviation of 0.31, and 2.46 for Liberal Arts majors with a standard deviation of 0.41. The T-test value of 5.72 and a significance value of 0.00 lead to the rejection of Ho, confirming a significant difference between the assessments of the two majors regarding the overall quality of practical teaching.

Assessment on Quality of Practical Teaching

Table 7. Overall Level of Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability

Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Global Innovative Thinking	2.64	0.52	Agree/ Satisfied
Entrepreneurial Literacy	2.59	0.47	Agree/ Satisfied
Practical Ability	2.64	0.45	Agree/ Satisfied
Over-All Mean	2.62	0.42	Agree/ Satisfied

Legend Scale: 3.51-4.00 Strongly Agree/Strongly Satisfied; 2.51-3.50 Agree/Satisfied; 1.51-2.50 Slightly Disagree/ Slightly Dissatisfied; 1.00-1.50 Disagree/Dissatisfied.

Table 7 presents the overall level of entrepreneurial innovative ability, evaluated through three main factors: Global Innovative Thinking, Entrepreneurial Literacy, and Practical Ability. Each factor is rated based on its mean score and standard deviation, accompanied by an interpretation.

The overall mean score across all factors is 2.62, with a standard deviation of 0.42, leading to an "Agree" interpretation. This comprehensive evaluation indicates a generally positive perception of entrepreneurial innovative ability among the respondents, suggesting that they feel confident in their skills and abilities across various dimensions of entrepreneurship.

Research by Yin, Liu and Tong (2022) points out that Chinese college students possess the core entrepreneurial competencies required for success, showing their overall satisfaction with their own innovation and entrepreneurial abilities.

The study of Zhao et al. (2022) points out that Chinese college students have a high overall evaluation of innovation and entrepreneurial ability, but a relatively weak performance in specific entrepreneurial literacy. This may be due to the fact that the implementation of

entrepreneurship education is not comprehensive and in-depth, especially in the training of practical skills and practical experience.

Differences in the Assessment of Respondents on the Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability

Table 8. *Differences in the Assessment of Respondents on the Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability according to Sex*

Factors	Sex	Mean	Std. Deviation	T-test value	Sig Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Global Innovative Thinking	Male	2.76	0.48	5.66	.000	Rejected	Significant
	Female	2.47	0.52				
Entrepreneurial Literacy	Male	2.72	0.40	6.09	.000	Rejected	Significant
	Female	2.42	0.51				
Practical Ability	Male	2.73	0.41	4.66	.000	Rejected	Significant
	Female	2.52	0.48				
Over-All Mean	Male	2.74	0.36	6.35	.000	Rejected	Significant
	Female	2.47	0.43				

Level of Significance at 0.05.

The overall mean score across all factors is 2.74 for males with a standard deviation of 0.36, and 2.47 for females with a standard deviation of 0.43.

The T-test value of 6.35 and a significance value of 0.000 lead to the rejection of Ho, confirming a significant difference between the assessments of male and female respondents regarding entrepreneurial innovative ability.

Table 9. *Differences in the Assessment of Respondents on the Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability according to Age*

Factors	Age	Mean	Std. Deviation	T-test value	Sig Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Global Innovative Thinking	18-20	2.52	0.53	-4.42	.000	Rejected	Significant
	Above 20	2.75	0.48				
Entrepreneurial Literacy	18-20	2.47	0.49	-5.05	.000	Rejected	Significant
	Above 20	2.71	0.43				
Practical Ability	18-20	2.51	0.48	-5.57	.000	Rejected	Significant
	Above 20	2.76	0.39				
Over-All Mean	18-20	2.50	0.42	-5.83	.000	Rejected	Significant
	Above 20	2.74	0.38				

Level of Significance at 0.05.

The overall mean score across all factors is 2.50 for respondents aged 18-20 with a standard deviation of 0.42, and 2.74 for those above 20 with a standard deviation of 0.38. The T-test value of -5.83 and a significance value of 0.000 lead to the rejection of Ho, confirming a significant difference between the assessments of the two age groups regarding entrepreneurial innovative ability.

Table 10. *Differences in the Assessment of Respondents on the Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability according to Academic Year*

Factors	Academic Year	Mean	Std. Deviation	F-test value	Sig Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Global Innovative Thinking	Freshman	2.56	0.59	3.32	0.02	Rejected	Significant
	Sophomore	2.58	0.46				
	Junior	2.70	0.47				
	Senior	2.77	0.54				
Entrepreneurial Literacy	Freshman	2.42	0.55	7.10	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Sophomore	2.62	0.41				
	Junior	2.62	0.47				
	Senior	2.73	0.41				
Practical Ability	Freshman	2.47	0.52	11.80	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Sophomore	2.60	0.39				
	Junior	2.73	0.43				
	Senior	2.84	0.37				
Over-All Mean	Freshman	2.48	0.47	8.50	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Sophomore	2.60	0.35				
	Junior	2.68	0.41				
	Senior	2.78	0.39				

Level of Significance at 0.05.

The overall mean score across all factors is 2.48 for freshmen with a standard deviation of 0.47, 2.60 for sophomores with a standard deviation of 0.35, 2.68 for juniors with a standard deviation of 0.41, and 2.78 for seniors with a standard deviation of 0.39.

The F-test value is 8.50 with a significance value of 0.00, leading to the rejection of Ho and confirming a significant difference among the academic years regarding entrepreneurial innovative ability.

Table 11. Differences in the Assessment of Respondents on the Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability according to Major of Study

Factors	Major of Study	Mean	Std. Deviation	T-test value	Sig Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Global Innovative Thinking	Science and Engineering	2.74	0.50	4.31	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Liberal Arts	2.52	0.51				
Entrepreneurial Literacy	Science and Engineering	2.71	0.39	5.67	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Liberal Arts	2.44	0.52				
Practical Ability	Science and Engineering	2.78	0.38	7.16	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Liberal Arts	2.46	0.47				
Over-All Mean	Science and Engineering	2.75	0.37	6.61	0.00	Rejected	Significant
	Liberal Arts	2.47	0.43				

Level of Significance at 0.05.

The overall mean score across all factors is 2.75 for Science and Engineering majors with a standard deviation of 0.37, and 2.47 for Liberal Arts majors with a standard deviation of 0.43. The T-test value of 6.61 and a significance value of 0.00 lead to the rejection of Ho, confirming a significant difference between the assessments of the two groups regarding entrepreneurial innovative ability.

Correlation Between Quality of Practical Teaching and Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability

Table 12. Correlation Between Quality of Practical Teaching and Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability

Factors	Practical Teaching Input	Practical Teaching Process	Practical Teaching Effect	Quality of Practical Teaching
Global Innovative Thinking	0.45**	0.71**	0.59**	0.65**
Entrepreneurial Literacy	0.54**	0.64**	0.59**	0.45**
Practical Ability	0.3**	0.54**	0.69**	0.61**
Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability	0.69**	0.60**	0.48**	0.69**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 12 presents the correlation between the quality of practical teaching and entrepreneurial innovative ability, focusing on four main factors: Practical Teaching Input, Practical Teaching Process, Practical Teaching Effect, and the overall Quality of Practical Teaching. The correlations are measured and reported for Global Innovative Thinking, Entrepreneurial Literacy, Practical Ability, and Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability.

For Global Innovative Thinking, there is a moderate correlation with Practical Teaching Input (0.45), a strong correlation with Practical Teaching Process (0.71), a moderate correlation with Practical Teaching Effect (0.59), and a strong correlation with the overall Quality of Practical Teaching (0.65). Xiao and Xue (2024) pointed out in their research that practical teaching allows students to accumulate experience through practical operation, helps students apply theoretical knowledge to practical problems, and thus stimulates their innovative thinking. Especially when it comes to international cooperation or cross-cultural projects, it can broaden students' global perspective and help them understand and accept different cultures and ways of thinking, thus stimulating global innovative thinking.

Entrepreneurial Literacy shows a moderate correlation with Practical Teaching Input (0.54), a moderate correlation with Practical Teaching Process (0.64), a moderate correlation with Practical Teaching Effect (0.59), and a moderate correlation with the overall Quality of Practical Teaching (0.45).

Practical Ability exhibits a lower correlation with Practical Teaching Input (0.3), a moderate correlation with Practical Teaching Process (0.54), a strong correlation with Practical Teaching Effect (0.69), and a strong correlation with the overall Quality of Practical Teaching (0.61).

Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability demonstrates a strong correlation with Practical Teaching Input (0.69), a moderate correlation with Practical Teaching Process (0.60), a moderate correlation with Practical Teaching Effect (0.48), and a strong correlation with the overall Quality of Practical Teaching (0.69). Wang, Gong and Men (2022) pointed out in their research that integrating innovation and entrepreneurship education into curriculum practice teaching is an important way to simultaneously improve students' professional quality, practical application ability and innovation and entrepreneurship ability. This requires teaching reform from the input of practical teaching, such as policy, class arrangement, teaching equipment and teachers' input.

Overall, these correlations indicate significant relationships between the quality of practical teaching and various aspects of entrepreneurial innovative ability, with the strongest correlations generally observed between Practical Teaching Process and Global Innovative Thinking, as well as between Practical Teaching Input and Entrepreneurial Innovative Ability. These findings suggest that improving the quality of practical teaching can positively impact entrepreneurial innovative abilities.

This research aims to examine the relationship between quality of practical teaching and students' entrepreneurial innovative ability at a macro level in the context of colleges in Hunan Province, China.

The assessment of student respondents regarding the quality of practical teaching revealed general satisfaction, but also highlighted

several areas for improvement. Students felt that the college's teaching concepts were not advanced enough, the qualifications of practical teaching instructors were not well-structured, and there were insufficient hours dedicated to practical teaching. Additionally, they noted that the content lacked scientific rigor, was not practical, and that assessment methods needed optimization. Ultimately, students believed practical teaching did not significantly enhance their professional competitiveness, indicating that expected learning outcomes were not met.

Analysis of differences in assessments based on student profiles showed no significant variances in practical teaching input and process across different grades. However, notable differences in practical teaching output were observed among students of various sexes, ages, and majors, suggesting targeted interventions could improve teaching quality.

Regarding entrepreneurial innovative ability, respondents expressed general satisfaction but identified weaknesses in skills such as problem analysis from multiple perspectives, flexible problem-solving, resource coordination, teamwork, interdisciplinary application, self-directed learning, and reflective practice. These insights pinpointed areas where colleges need to strengthen their programs.

Further analysis revealed significant differences in entrepreneurial abilities when considering factors like sex, age, grade, and major, indicating that tailored support could enhance students' innovation and entrepreneurship skills.

Finally, a Pearson correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between the quality of practical teaching and students' entrepreneurial innovative ability. The strongest correlations were found between the practical teaching process and global innovative thinking, as well as between practical teaching input and entrepreneurial innovation ability. Overall, improving the quality of practical teaching positively influences students' entrepreneurial capabilities, suggesting that enhancements in this area could lead to better educational outcomes and professional preparedness.

Conclusions

The quality of practical teaching varied according to sex, age, and major, suggesting that educators could intervene based on these factors to improve teaching quality. There is a need to strengthen abilities in problem analysis, flexible problem solving, resource integration, team cooperation, interdisciplinary application, independent learning, and reflective summary. Educators should also address factors such as global innovative thinking, entrepreneurial literacy, and practical ability to promote innovation and entrepreneurship. Overall, improving the quality of practical teaching had a positive impact on enhancing the entrepreneurial and innovative abilities of the students. According to the results of this study, the development program for improving the quality of practical teaching are as follows.

Enhancing teaching concepts and staff structure involves updating and introducing advanced teaching methods that emphasize the integration of theory and practice, fostering students' innovative thinking. This requires adjusting the age and expertise of the teaching staff by recruiting more young teachers and industry experts while providing ongoing training to improve their practical teaching skills.

Optimizing class hours and course design is essential. Increasing practical teaching hours and thoughtfully arranging course schedules will ensure a balanced integration of theory and practice. Additionally, course content should be redesigned to be more scientifically grounded and aligned with industry needs, with timely adjustments based on market developments.

Promoting interdisciplinary learning and diverse teaching methods is crucial. Offering interdisciplinary practical courses will enhance students' resource coordination and problem-solving skills. Furthermore, enriching practical teaching through team projects, competitions, and self-study initiatives, along with optimizing assessment methods to include varied approaches like project reviews and case analyses, will contribute to student development.

Integrating innovation and entrepreneurship into practical teaching is important. This integration focuses on their correlation with practical abilities and emphasizes strengthening school-enterprise partnerships to enhance students' professional competitiveness while ensuring effective management of the practical teaching process.

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